

Deepfakes, Brain Emulation, and Things We Are: Asserting Rights of Origination (Extended Abstract)

Jeremy A. Hansen

Norwich University
158 Harmon Dr.
Northfield, VT 05663 USA

Introduction

A cornerstone of information security is authentication, the process by which a person proves their identity. Authentication is typically described as having three possible methods (or factors) for a person to supply this proof: one involving something the person knows (like a password), another involving something the person has (like a key), and a third involving something inherent to the person themselves (like a fingerprint).

By organizing personal rights under three categories parallel to the methods of proving one's identity, this work introduces a theory of rights of *origination* encompassing rights like privacy, bodily integrity, and publicity. These rights are based on a natural person's attributes that originate in and are inherent to their physical body or actions and connected to neither tangible property nor intangible but otherwise *separable* artifacts like intellectual property. This work sketches an outline of personality- and identity-based rights to identify where current law may not consistently address threats to human rights in light of technological changes.

Though the specifics of our discussion here are derived from US law, there are common rights guaranteed by multiple supranational organizations that fall under the umbrella of origination: rights of dignity, privacy, reputation, and physical integrity (United Nations General Assembly 1948; European Convention 2000).

Right of Publicity

The right of *publicity* (Rothman 2018) is the established right in US law best suited to be the foundation for a proposed right of origination. It safeguards recognizable aspects of one's identity from unauthorized commercial use. With this right, people can assert control over the use of their inherent personal characteristics in creative works (in copyright law), the use of their name or personal marks in trade (in trademark law), or their independent right of publicity (in laws prohibiting defamation, for example).

Rothman notes that the complexity of and conflicts between laws relating to identity-based rights create a tangled *identity thicket* (Rothman 2022). Because of competing state and federal jurisdictions in the US, it is unclear whether publicity is a property right or a

privacy-based personal right. Although it has historically been considered a personal right, publicity has increasingly become a transferable intellectual property right that can be bought and sold (Rothman 2018). When one's right of publicity becomes commodified, parts of the person's identity can become legally separate from that person, with the identity-holder and the publicity-holder no longer being the same entity. When publicity is property, it can be lost in bankruptcy, sold postmortem to pay off debts, used as collateral, split in divorce, or cashed out in hard times. Allowing such transfers "impairs the rights to liberty, freedom of speech, and freedom of association" (Rothman 2018). Ensuring that such rights are inalienable and rooted in the individual can prevent many of these negative effects.

Rights of Origination

The right to publicity leaves out several rights that are based on personality and/or inherent personal characteristics. We define rights of origination as protecting all personality-based interests and attributes inherent to a natural person. Individuals thus maintain control over the use of the various parts of their inseparable identity and the right to prevent unauthorized use. Intellectual property, tangible property, and labor are not included in this definition because they are either physically separable from or not inherent to a person's identity. We assert that, absent a compelling ethical case, rights of origination should be universal and inalienable.

Deepfakes & Simulations

Deepfakes or digital replicas are software-generated simulations of people that use existing images, audio, and/or video to produce convincing but entirely synthetic content. Given a corpus of high-resolution video of an actor, for example, it is possible to construct (without their consent or physical presence) convincing simulated video scenes with that actor. Deepfakes lack proper regulation in part due to First Amendment and jurisdictional concerns, with only a few US states regulating their use in specific contexts. These regulations may only be enforceable through existing bans on obscenity, copyright infringement, or defamation. Simulations built from the data of multiple people pose an additional challenge. For example, if a text-based chatbot is

a simulated amalgamation of two celebrities, it is not clear whether either celebrity would be able to assert any rights.

Uploads & Emulations

Where simulations were artificial and approximate versions of a person based on sources external to the person, brain emulations are effectively copies of the person—executing in a computer the actual physical state of a person (the *donor*) whose brain has been scanned at an extremely high level of detail. We do not explore here whether this is feasible but given the interest in both popular culture and the literature (Irwin 2019; Eckersley and Sandberg 2013; Sandberg and Bostrom 2008), it is worthwhile to consider social and legal impacts of a disruptive technology like this.

The donor being scanned for emulation should have rights of origination, and third parties involved in the process should have clear responsibilities to the donor. In particular, informed consent must be secured before such scans, and they should be treated like biological samples, clones, or derived tissue to conform with (for example) the CFR’s “prohibition on making the human body and its parts as such a source of financial gain” (European Convention 2000).

The brain scan captures the entirety of the donor’s identity, leading to profound privacy violations if unauthorized access occurs. If thoughts, memories, opinions, or secrets can be extracted, heightened security is needed. Potential issues with emulations are discussed in (Eckersley and Sandberg 2013), and the donor should have the rights to address any such infringement. It is not clear that any extant laws would apply well in this case.

Conclusion

With rights of origination, *every* person would have the ability to restrict the use of the characteristics inherent to their identity, whether in simulations, emulations, or more prosaic situations. We hope that this is the beginning of a discussion, but many open questions remain:

- Are there elements of rights of origination that should be in the public domain?
- Is there fair use with deepfakes? With emulations?
- Are donors responsible for the behavior of their emulation?
- Are there socially beneficial and reasonable restrictions on donors or emulations?

References

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